

APPENDIX: HOW IS FIG. 3 OBTAINED ANALYTICALLY

In the paper, Fig. 3 is presented, which has been obtained analytically. It represents the average number of bytes required by the samples of an AC and a DC signal, as a function of its amplitude. They are two piecewise defined functions, with four intervals each.

A. AC signal

1) Interval ($2^{24} < A < 2^{31} - 1$)

Fig. 6 represents the case in which the maximum amplitude A requires 4 bytes to be expressed.

Fig. 6. Signal that requires 4 bytes.

In this case, we have the following equations:

$$2^8 - 1 = A \sin(x_1) \quad (1)$$

$$2^{16} - 1 = A \sin(x_2) \quad (2)$$

$$2^{24} - 1 = A \sin(x_3) \quad (3)$$

The average number of bytes N required by a sample, can be obtained depending on the probability of being on each of the four zones of the signal:

$$E[N \mid 2^{24} < A < 2^{31} - 1] = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[4 \cdot \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - x_3 \right) + 3 \cdot (x_3 - x_2) + 2 \cdot (x_2 - x_1) + 1 \cdot x_1 \right] \quad (4)$$

Using (1), (2) and (3), we can express (4) as:

$$E[N \mid 2^{24} < A < 2^{31} - 1] = \frac{2}{\pi} \left[2\pi - \arcsin\left(\frac{2^{24}-1}{A}\right) - \arcsin\left(\frac{2^{16}-1}{A}\right) - \arcsin\left(\frac{2^8-1}{A}\right) \right] \quad (5)$$

2) Interval ($2^{16} < A < 2^{24} - 1$)

In Fig.7 the case in which the signal requires up to 3 bytes ($2^{16} < A < 2^{24} - 1$) is presented.

Fig. 7. Signal that requires 3 bytes.

In this case, we have the following equations:

$$2^8 - 1 = A \sin(x_1) \quad (6)$$

$$2^{16} - 1 = A \sin(x_2) \quad (7)$$

The average number of bytes required by a sample, can be obtained depending on the probability of being on each of the three zones of the signal:

$$E[N | 2^{16} < A < 2^{24} - 1] = \frac{1}{\frac{\pi}{2}} \left[3 \cdot \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - x_2 \right) + 2 \cdot (x_2 - x_1) + 1 \cdot x_1 \right] \quad (8)$$

Using (6) and (7), we can express (8) as:

$$E[N | 2^{16} < A < 2^{24} - 1] = \frac{2}{\pi} \left[\frac{3\pi}{2} - \arcsin\left(\frac{2^{16}-1}{A}\right) - \arcsin\left(\frac{2^8-1}{A}\right) \right] \quad (9)$$

3) Interval ($2^8 < A < 2^{16} - 1$)

In Fig.8, the case in which the signal requires up to 2 bytes ($2^8 < A < 2^{16} - 1$) is presented.

Fig. 8. Signal that requires 2 bytes.

In this case, we have the following equation:

$$2^8 - 1 = A \sin(x_1) \quad (10)$$

The average number of bytes required by a sample, can be obtained depending on the probability of being on each of the two zones of the signal:

$$E[N | 2^8 < A < 2^{16} - 1] = \frac{1}{\frac{\pi}{2}} \left[2 \cdot \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - x_1 \right) + 1 \cdot x_1 \right] \quad (11)$$

Using (10), we can express (11) as:

$$E[N | 2^8 < A < 2^{16} - 1] = \frac{2}{\pi} \left[\pi - \arcsin\left(\frac{2^8-1}{A}\right) \right] \quad (12)$$

4) *Interval* ($A < 2^8$)

In this interval, the signal will always require one byte.

$$E[N \mid A < 2^8] = 1 \quad (13)$$

B. *DC signal*

In the case of a DC signal, things are more straightforward:

$$E[N \mid 2^{24} < A < 2^{31} - 1] = 4 \quad (14)$$

$$E[N \mid 2^{16} < A < 2^{24} - 1] = 3 \quad (15)$$

$$E[N \mid 2^8 < A < 2^{16} - 1] = 2 \quad (16)$$

$$E[N \mid A < 2^8] = 1 \quad (17)$$